

Understand the Burden of MDR TB in DHQ/Teaching Hospital Gujranwala

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Abstract:

Resistance to anti-tuberculosis (TB) medicines is a major public health threat in most countries of the World. As small no. of representative and quality-assured information on the magnitude of this problem existed in Pakistan, a survey was conducted in the DHQ/Teaching Hospital Gujranwala. Between January 2017 and January 2018, 212 consecutively diagnosed new culture-positive TB patients residing in District Gujranwala were enrolled in the survey. Mycobacterium tuberculosis isolates were obtained from each patient and tested for susceptibility to Rifampin Resistant. Multidrug-resistant (MDR)-TB was found in 19.2% of new patients. Overall, nearly one in 8 patients enrolled had MDR-TB. Patients with less than 25 yrs of age have shown a higher odds ratio of multi-drug resistant TB than those aged >55 yrs. The findings of this survey in Gujranwala District are alarming and represent the high proportions of MDR-TB. This study greatly contributes to the understanding of the burden of drug-resistant TB in urban areas of Gujranwala

Keywords: *Epidemiology, Gujranwala Medical College Gujranwala, multidrug-resistant tuberculosis, surveillance*

Introduction

Globally, tuberculosis (TB) is one of the leading causes of death due to an infectious disease, second only to HIV/AIDS [1, 2]. Estimates suggest that approximately one-third of the world's population is infected with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, the microbe that causes TB, and ~10% of infected individuals will develop active TB at some point in their lives. For individuals also infected with HIV, the likelihood of developing active TB after infection is much higher [3, 4]. In 2006, ~9.2 million people globally developed active TB, and it is estimated that 1.7 million people died as a result of TB, including 200,000 HIV-infected individuals [1]. Although estimates suggest that the rates of new cases and deaths due to TB show signs of slowing throughout the world, recent increases in rates of drug-resistant TB have the potential to reverse these gains [1, 3].

In 2006, an estimated 500,000 individuals throughout the world developed multidrug-resistant (MDR) TB, (MDR)-TB (defined as TB caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* resistant to isoniazid and rifampicin) [5] and extensively drug-resistant (XDR)-TB (defined as MDR-TB plus resistance to fluoroquinolones and at least one second-line injectable agent) [5], has been increasingly documented and may jeopardise the achievements made to date in controlling the community and nosocomial spread of *M. tuberculosis* strains [6]

Of the approximately 510,000 patients diagnosed with TB each year in Pakistan, nearly majority have a bacteriologically confirmed diagnosis, and 15000 developed MDR TB each year, is ranked fifth among B high burden countries worldwide, and it accounts 61% of the burden in the WHO Eastern Mediterranean Region. The Country also estimated to have the fourth highest prevalence of Multidrug-Resistant (MDR TB) Globally. Patients with drug-sensitive TB are treated with the standard regimen proposed by the World Health Organization (WHO) since 2009 [7], with a treatment success rate for new smear-positive cases of 75% in that year.

Very high frequencies of MDR-TB have been documented in nearby countries, including the India Bangladesh and Indonesia. Given that Pakistan was one of the Country with small sufficiently representative and quality-assured data on the magnitude of drug resistance, Pakistan decided to undertake a drug-resistance survey following WHO recommendations. The city of Pakistan, with a population of 5.2 million people, was selected as the target area for this study. The survey aimed to investigate levels and

patterns of resistance to Rifampin anti-TB drugs among new and previously treated TB cases and to explore risk factors for the development of drug resistance. Herein, we present the results of this survey.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Between January 2017 and January 2018 a survey to investigate anti-TB drug resistance was implemented in the District Gujranwala DHQ/Teaching Hospital Gujranwala. The study was designed to generate representative information on drug resistance among all patients with TB in the District. All consecutive patients with newly diagnosed and previously treated culture-positive pulmonary TB residing in District Gujranwala for more than 12 months and registered in TB center DHQ/Teaching Hospital were invited to take part in the study. Only patients residing in District Gujranwala for more than 12 months were considered eligible for enrolment to avoid the risk of including subjects living in other parts of the country who could have traveled to the capital city after diagnosis to seek better healthcare. New patients were defined as those without a history of prior treatment with first-line anti-TB drugs (isoniazid rifampicin, ethambutol, and Pyrazinamide), or those having received prior treatment for less than,1 month; previously treated TB cases were those who had received prior first-line anti-TB treatment for more than 1 month [7,8]. Informed consent was obtained from patients before enrolment into the study. The following variables were collected for each patient through a clinician-led interview performed during sputum collection: sex; age; country of birth; treatment history (new/previously treated, including subcategory of previous treatment); education (university/college/secondary school/primary school or lower); size of household (number of persons living in the same house); and history of smoking in the past 5 yrs. Medical records were reviewed to confirm the reliability of the information on previous treatment history gathered during the interview. A random sample of patients (nearly 40% of the total) was re-interviewed during later monitoring visits to assess the quality of the answers provided in the initial interviews.

Re-interviews showed full concordance with treatment history information obtained during the initial

interviews. Only patients with a positive culture were included in the analysis. Patients with only clinical and/or radiological diagnosis of TB, extrapulmonary TB cases, cases of TB caused by mycobacteria other than *M. tuberculosis*, and patients having already received more than one re-treatment regimen were excluded. The ethics committee of the review board Pulmonology and Tuberculosis Department reviewed and approved the survey protocol. Two sputum specimens were collected from each patient. Isolation and identification were performed on AFB appearance. Isolates of *M. tuberculosis* were examined with Gene Xpert. The routine external quality assurance system for Rifampicin susceptibility testing at the DHQ/Teaching Hospital Gujranwala Laboratory includes annual proficiency testing and regular on-site monitoring missions . In the proficiency testing, exercise Data were entered into Table form, and the results are collected from the survey.

Results

During the intake period, a total of 465 patients were notified in the District Gujranwala DHQ/Teaching Hospital Gujranwala. Of the 212 (50.5%) met the inclusion criteria of the survey (culture-positive pulmonary TB). Drug susceptibility tests could be performed for 200 (94.3%) of these patients. 12 (5.7%) patients had to be excluded because of culture contamination, and Of the remaining 200 patients, 144 (67.9%) were new TB cases, and 68 (32.1%) were patients with a history of previous TB treatment; 112 (52.8%) were male. Data on history of TB treatment and additional characteristics of the study population are shown in table 1.

Table 1 Characteristics of tuberculosis patients

	Male	Female	All
Total subjects	112(52.8)	100(47.2)	212(100.0)
Age group yrs			
<24	30(14.2)	25(11.8)	55(26.0)
24–34	32(15.1)	24(11.3)	56(26.4)
35–44	20(9.4)	18(8.5)	38(17.9)
45-54	14(6.6)	15(7.1)	29(13.7)
55-64	9(4.2)	10(4.7)	19(8.9)
>64	7(3.3)	8(3.8)	15(7.1)
Treatment history			
New	80(37.7)	64(30.2)	144(67.9)
Previously Treated	38(17.9)	30(14.2)	68(32.1)

Data are presented as n (%) unless otherwise stated

Of these cases, 5 (19.2%) were newly diagnosed that was resistant to Rifampicin, and 21 (80.8%) previously treated cases were found to have rifampicin resistant with a major predisposition of a young age to 45 years of age.

TABLE 2 Resistances to Rifampin

Age Group	New	Previously treated	All
<24	2(7.7)	6(23.1)	8(34.6)
24-34	1(3.8)	5(19.2)	6(26.9)
35-44	1(3.8)	5(19.2)	6(23.0)
45-54	1(3.8)	2(7.7)	3(11.5)
55-64	0	2(7.7)	2(7.7)
>64	0	1(3.8)	1(3.8)

Data are presented as n (%) unless otherwise stated

And the risk factors for this MDR shows following results it shows that the family with more members have a high rate of both TB and MDR TB and also shows that the educated people have less no of chances of Tb as compare to uneducated or less educated. And it shows that new cases have fewer chances of MDR TB as compare to Previously Treated patients.

TABLE 3 Risk factors for multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB)

	Tested n	MDR TB %
Sex		
Male	112(52.8)	16(61.5)
Female	100(47.2)	10(38.5)
Age group yrs		
<24	55(26.0)	8(34.6)
24-34	56(26.4)	6(26.9)
35-44	38(17.9)	6(23.0)
45-54	29(13.7)	3(11.5)
55-64	19(8.9)	2(7.7)
>64	15(7.1)	1(3.8)
Treatment history		
New	144(67.9)	5(19.2)
Previously Treated	68(14.2)	21(80.8)
Education		
University	2(1.0)	0(0.0)
College	10(4.7)	2(7.7)
Secondary School	65(30.7)	7(26.9)
Primary School or lower	120(56.6)	15(57.7)
Unknow	15(7.1)	2(7.7)
House Hold		
3	12	0
4	18	2
5	67	8
>5	110	15
unknown	5	1
Smoking in last 5 years		
No	150	18
Yes	58	6
Unknown	4	2

Data are presented as n (%) unless otherwise stated

Discussion

This study has revealed moderately high levels of drug-resistant TB in the District Gujranwala DHQ/Teaching Hospital Gujranwala. The proportions of new and previously treated TB cases found to have MDR-TB (19.2% and 80.8%, respectively) are the almost equal record anywhere in the world in the history

of the WHO Global Project on Anti-tuberculosis Drug Resistance Surveillance [9, 10]. The very high frequency of drug-resistant forms of TB

indicates the existence of serious problems in the organization of TB treatment in Gujranwala, as well as in Pakistan overall. The turbulent years following the drug shortages and previously unseen social problems and poverty and also the loss of compliance. As a result, a significant pool of drug-resistant strains emerged that continue to limit the success of the National TB control programme today, as we are still being confronted by several challenges.

First, the outpatient phase of TB treatment, and particularly MDR-TB treatment, is not managed strongly enough: in some locations where patients receive ambulatory treatment, costly second-line drugs are difficult to purchase. Ambulatory patients on any treatment regimen, first or second line, frequently default due to the inconvenience or cost of traveling to obtain drugs and having to miss work, as well as coexisting social problems, including uncontrolled Smoking, which is common among TB patients in this region of the world.

Secondly, infection control measures in TB hospitals and dispensaries, including administrative and individual protection measures, are frequently insufficient, resulting in transmission of strains from drug-resistant to drug-susceptible patients.

The magnitude of the problem of drug-resistant TB does not come as a complete surprise for the country, given its relatively advanced nationwide surveillance system that routinely tests for drug susceptibility in many laboratories and centrally collects data at the TB control Department of Pakistan. This system has shown proportions of drug resistance increasingly in recent years (e.g., 19.8% of MDR-TB among new cases in District Gujranwala DHQ/Teaching Hospital Gujranwala) [11-14]. However, the study described

herein has ensured high-quality testing, centrally performed at the National TB Reference Laboratory and confirmed by the partner Supranational TB Reference Laboratory, and careful collection of accurate patient treatment history information. When disaggregating previously treated TB cases by subcategory, frequencies of MDR-TB were found to be significantly higher among relapse cases than new TB cases, 80.8% versus 19.2%, respectively. This difference reflects that weakness may exist in procedures for declaring patients successfully treated, i.e., such patients were not successfully treated for TB in the first place due to remaining drug-resistant bacteria, and/or that inadequate infection control measures may be commonly causing TB patients to be re-infected with their fellow patients' drug-resistant strains during hospitalisation and poor compliance of the patients.

A single data point in time, as has been provided in this survey, cannot answer the question of whether the situation of drug-resistant TB is getting better or worse in the city. However, the higher prevalence of MDR-TB among the younger age groups of previously untreated TB cases is an indication of a possible increasing transmission of MDR-TB strains, as previously untreated TB cases from older age and poor compliance. When we compare the study with another study in Minsk Belarus, we found that the lower no of MDR TB as compare to that study and incidence is 19.8% MDR TB in new cases in our study as compared to 35.3% in Minsk and 80.8% in previously treated cases versus 64.7% in Minsk. In our study, it shows the clear relation of no of family members with TB and MDR TB as compare to that study and also it is more in illiterate and less educated people which is not the case in Minsk.

Conclusion

From the above study, it is concluded that every year round about 212 new patients diagnosed as TB in DHQ/Teaching Hospital Gujranwala and almost average 26 patients diagnosed as MDR TB from which 5(19.8%) new and 21(80.8%) previously treated Patients. The study shows greater predisposition in young and middle-aged person as compared to older patients, and it showed the greater impact of household size and literacy rate, and also it depends on the poor compliance of the patients.

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